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The Relationship Between Carotid Intima-Media Thickness and Mean Platelet Volume in Patients with Nephrotic Syndrome

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Abstract: The prevalence of cardiovascular disease is increased in patients diagnosed with nephrotic syndrome. Atherosclerosis is a pathological process that causes cardiovascular, cerebral, and peripheral artery disease. Carotid artery intima-media thickness is commonly used in the assessment of atherosclerosis. Mean platelet volume is a novel marker associated with atherothrombosis. In this study, we aimed to determine the relationship between mean platelet volume, which may be an indicator of atherosclerosis, and carotid artery intima-media thickness in patients with nephrotic syndrome at our clinic. The data of the 30 patients diagnosed with nephrotic syndrome who applied to the nephrology clinic were retrospectively reviewed. The patients' demographic characteristics, laboratory results, blood pressure measurements, and treatments received were recorded. Since the study was planned retrospectively, the sample size was not calculated. Descriptive statistics were used in the analysis of the data. Descriptive statistics were expressed as mean, standard deviation, minimum, maximum, number (n), and percentage (%). The SPSS statistical package program (IBM SPSS for Windows, ver. 25) was used in all of the analyses, and a $p < 0.05$ value was considered significant. In our retrospective study, 14 (46%) of the 30 patients were male and 16 (54%) were female. Plaque was detected in 7 (23%) of these 30 patients, while 23 (77%) had no plaque. The mean age in the group with plaque was 52.8 years, while it was 38.5 years in the group without plaque. A significant difference was found between the group with plaque and the group without plaque in terms of age ($p < 0.05$). The mean platelet volume was 9.8 in the group with plaque and 10.08 in the group without plaque. The left carotid artery intima-media thickness was 0.9 fl in the group with plaque and 0.88 fl in the group without plaque. The right carotid artery intima-media thickness was 1.03 fl in the group with plaque and 0.86 fl in the group without plaque. The right carotid artery intima-media thickness was found to be thicker than the left. Nephrotic syndrome is a major cause of chronic kidney damage. The incidence of cardiovascular disease is high in patients with nephrotic syndrome. Both carotid artery intima-media thickness and mean platelet volume are predictive factors for atherosclerosis.

Introduction

Nephrotic Syndrome (NS) is characterized by massive proteinuria (>3.5 g/day), edema, hypoalbuminemia, hyperlipidemia, and hypercoagulability. Its pathogenesis involves many factors, including antibodies, the complement pathway, coagulation factors, leukocytes, and intrinsic renal cells [1]. In patients diagnosed with NS, the incidence of cardiovascular disease has increased in association with hypercoagulopathy, proteinuria, low serum albumin levels, and dyslipidemia [2]. Carotid artery intima-media thickness (IMT) appears before plaque development. It has predictive value for atherosclerosis development and is widely used in the assessment of atherosclerosis [3]. The mean platelet volume (MPV) ranges from 7.5 to 12.0 fl (femtoliters). The percentage of large platelets constitutes 0.2-5.0% of the total platelet population [4], and it has been observed that high MPV may be an independent high mortality risk factor in patients after acute ischemic cardiac events [5]. MPV has been found to be a predictor of severe atherosclerosis and is thought to be useful for predicting and identifying cardiac risks in patients with coronary artery disease [6].

Methods

Ethical committee approval was obtained from the Ethics Committee Presidency of the Dursun Odabaşı Medical Center at Van Yüzüncü Yıl University on 20/01/2023 with the number 2023/01-10. The study was planned retrospectively. Thirty patients diagnosed with nephrotic syndrome in the nephrology clinic were included in the study. Carotid Doppler ultrasound was performed on patients using the ACUSON S2000 ULTRASOUND SYSTEM (Siemens Solutions, Mountain View, CA, USA) 14L5 Ultrasound Linear Probe between January 2021 and August 2022, as recorded in the hospital's Enlil system. Data on the mean platelet volume measured by electrical impedance were obtained using automated hematology analyzers in the hematology laboratory.

Inclusion criteria: Diagnosis of nephrotic syndrome, at 18 years of age or older

Exclusion criteria for the study: Being under 18 years of age, being over 90 years of age, having undergone a kidney transplant, undergoing hemodialysis, having a glomerular filtration rate below 30 ml/min, being pregnant

Results

Thirty patients were included in the study. 14 (46%) were male and 16 (54%) were female. Plaque was present in 7 (23%) patients, while 23 (77%) had no plaque. The mean age was 52.8 in the group with plaque and 38.5 in the group without plaque. The presence of plaque was significant in older patients ($p < 0.05$). The normal range for MPV in our hospital laboratory system was 9.3-12.1 fl. Patients with MPV above 12.1 fl were considered positive. The mean MPV was 9.8 in the group with plaque and 10.08 in the group without plaque. There was no significant difference in MPV values between the groups. Left CIMT was 0.9 fl in the group with plaque and 0.88 fl in the group without plaque. Right LMCA was measured as 1.03 fl in the group with plaque and 0.86 fl in the group without plaque. There was no significant difference in right and left ICM values between the groups, but the right ICM was found to be thicker than the left. The mean blood pressure in the plaque group was measured as 121/74 mmHg, while it was 123/76 mmHg in the non-plaque group. No significant differences were found between the groups in other variables; the groups showed similar characteristics (Table 1).

Table 1. Comparison of demographic, clinical, and laboratory findings of patients according to the presence of plaque

	Plaque present (n:7)		Plaque absent (n:23)		P value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Age(years)	52,86	10,67	38,52	10,73	0,004
Hemoglobin (g/dl)	14,29	2,06	14,49	1,58	0,786
MCV (fl)	84,71	4,68	84,3	4,19	0,827
MPV (fl)	9,89	0,86	10,08	0,91	0,615
Neutrophils (ul)	4540	1205	5212	3091	0,582
Lymphocytes (ul)	2240	792	2184	661	0,854
Platelets (ul)	297714,3	64401,64	284859,6	61459,01	0,636
Creatinine (mg/dl)	1,17	0,52	0,96	0,57	0,397
Albumin (g/l)	41,71	7,74	40,7	7,89	0,766
Proteinuria (g/day)	2,2	3,94	2,1	3,5	0,949
LDL (mg/dl)	108,57	19,43	115,74	64,32	0,776
CRP (mg/l)	7,33	11,16	14,7	19,5	0,111
Systolic BP (mmHg)	121	29,86	123,43	21,43	0,812
Diastolic BP(mmHg)	74	10,54	76,35	12,16	0,649
Left CIMT (mm)	0,9	0,26	0,88	0,28	0,886
Right CIMT (mm)	1,03	0,45	0,86	0,26	0,211

Note: Bold p-values indicate statistically significant differences ($p < 0,05$)

MCV: mean Corpuscular Volume, MPV: mean platelet volume, LDL: low density lipoprotein,

CRP: C-reactive protein, CIMT: Carotid Intima-Media Thickness

The relationship and distribution between patients' "certain categorical measurements" and "presence of plaque" are shown in Table 2. Two of the men (14.3%) had plaque, while the remaining 12 (85.7%) did not. Five of the women (31.3%) had plaques, while the remaining 11 (68.7%) did not. The etiology was known for all patients in the group with plaques. The most common diagnosis in these patients was membranous glomerulonephritis (MGN) (n:5). The etiological distribution of the group without plaques was MGN (n=8), focal segmental glomerulosclerosis (FSGS) (n=4), idiopathic (n=4), IgA nephropathy (n=2), IgM nephropathy (n=1), and minimal change disease (MDD) (n=1). Only one patient had a diagnosis of diabetes mellitus (DM), and plaques were present in that patient. Plaques were detected in one of the two patients with cardiovascular disease (CVD) (Table 2).

The smokers were 23% (n=7) of the entire group. Plaque was detected in 14.3% (n=1) of smokers. Plaque was present in 26% of non-smokers. The vast majority of patients were not taking medication. Angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors, angiotensin receptor blockers, and immunosuppressants were the most commonly used medications. Twenty percent of patients were taking statins. Plaque was present in 2 of these patients (33.3%) (Table 2).

Table 2. Relationship between selected categorical variables and plaque presence

		Plaque present		Plaque absent		<i>P</i>
		n (7)	%	n (23)	%	
Gender	Male	2	14,3	12	85,7	<i>0,273</i>
	Female	5	31,3	11	68,8	
Primary disease	FSGS	0	0	4	100	<i>0,559</i>
	IgA nephropathy	1	33,3	2	66,7	
	IgM nephropathy	0	0	1	100	
	MGN	5	38,5	8	61,5	
	MPGN	1	25	3	75	
	Minimal change disease	0	0	1	100	
	Idiopathic	0	0	4	100	
CVD	present	1	50	1	50	<i>0,356</i>
	absent	6	21,4	22	78,6	
Diabetes mellitus	present	1	100	0	0	<i>0,065</i>
	absent	6	20,7	23	79,3	
Smoking	yes	1	14,3	6	85,7	<i>0,518</i>
	no	6	26,1	17	73,9	
Other medications	yes	2	28,6	5	71,4	<i>0,708</i>
	no	5	21,7	18	78,3	
Statin	yes	2	33,3	4	66,7	<i>0,517</i>
	no	5	20,8	19	79,2	

Significance levels were evaluated using the Chi-square test

Note: Bold *p*-values indicate statistically significant differences ($p < 0,05$)

FSGS: Focal Segmental Glomerulosclerosis, **MGN:** Membranous Glomerulonephritis **MPGN:** Membranoproliferative Glomerulonephritis, **CVD:** Cardiovascular Disease

The relationship and distribution between patients' "certain categorical measurements" and "carotid intima-media thickness" are shown in Table 3. In patients with plaque, the left CIMT was measured as an average of 0.59 fl, while the right CIMT was measured as an average of 0.61 fl. In patients without plaque, the left CIMT was 0.62 fl, while the right CIMT was 0.61 fl. No significant difference was found. In men, the left CIMT was 0.6, while the right CIMT was 0.6. In women, the left CIMT was measured as 0.62 fl, and the right CIMT as 0.63 fl. In those with CHD, the right and left CIMT were measured as the same, with an average of 0.75 fl. In those diagnosed with diabetes mellitus, the left CIMT was measured as 0.4 fl, and the right CIMT as 0.67 fl. In patients who smoked, the left CIMT was 0.64 and the right CIMT was 0.61 fl. In patients who did not smoke, the left CIMT was 0.6 and the right CIMT was 0.61 fl, and no significant difference was found. No significant difference was found between the right and left CIMT measurements in patients using statins (Table 3).

Table 3. Relationship between selected categorical variables and carotid intima–media thickness							
		<i>Left CIMT</i>			<i>Right CIMT</i>		
		Mean	SD	<i>P value</i>	Mean	SD	<i>P value</i>
Presence of plaque	present	0,59	0,18	<i>0,640</i>	0,61	0,13	<i>0,968</i>
	absent	0,62	0,11		0,61	0,12	
Gender	Male	0,60	0,10	<i>0,631</i>	0,60	0,09	<i>0,533</i>
	Female	0,62	0,15		0,63	0,14	
CVD	present	0,75	0,07	<i>0,106</i>	0,75	0,04	<i>0,091</i>
	absent	0,60	0,12		0,60	0,12	
Diabetes mellitus	present	0,40	0,02	<i>0,086</i>	0,67	0,03	<i>0,632</i>
	absent	0,62	0,12		0,61	0,12	
Smoking	yes	0,64	0,11	<i>0,521</i>	0,61	0,11	<i>0,968</i>
	no	0,60	0,13		0,61	0,12	
Other medications	yes	0,58	0,14	<i>0,419</i>	0,64	0,11	<i>0,543</i>
	no	0,62	0,12		0,61	0,12	
Statin	yes	0,54	0,11	<i>0,104</i>	0,64	0,08	<i>0,514</i>
	no	0,63	0,12		0,61	0,13	

Note: Bold *p*-values indicate statistically significant differences ($p < 0,05$).
SD: Standard deviation *CIMT:* Carotid Intima–Media Thickness, *CVD:* Cardiovascular Disease

The results of comparing patients' demographic, clinical, and laboratory findings "according to carotid intima-media thickness" are shown in Table 4. There is an inverse relationship between age and CIMT. While there is a linear relationship between hemoglobin and left CIMT, there is a negative relationship with right CIMT. MPV is inversely related to both left and right CIMT. As CIMT increases, MPV decreases. There is a linear relationship between CIMT and platelet count and creatinine. As MCV and neutrophil count increase, CIMT decreases. Systolic and diastolic blood pressure are inversely related to CIMT. Albumin has a linear relationship with left CIMT, while right CIMT has an inverse relationship (Table 4).

Table 4. Correlation between demographic, clinical, and laboratory parameters and carotid intima–media thickness

		Left CIMT	Right CIMT
Age(years)	<i>r</i>	-0,042	-0,031
Hemoglobin (g/dl)	<i>r</i>	0,218	-0,022
MCV (fl)	<i>r</i>	-0,157	-0,135
MPV (fl)	<i>r</i>	-0,225	-0,096
Neutrophils (ul)	<i>r</i>	-0,183	-0,153
Lymphocytes (ul)	<i>r</i>	0,126	-0,095
Platelets (ul)	<i>r</i>	0,167	0,142
Creatinine (mg/dl)	<i>r</i>	0,025	0,046
Albumin (g/l)	<i>r</i>	0,044	-0,013
Proteinuria (g/day)	<i>r</i>	-0,011	0,034
LDL (mg/dl)	<i>r</i>	-0,013	0,017
Systolic BP (mmHg)	<i>r</i>	-0,064	-0,073
Diastolic BP(mmHg)	<i>r</i>	-0,156	-0,198

CIMT: Carotid Intima–Media Thickness MCV: mean Corpuscular Volume, MPV: mean platelet volume, LDL: low density lipoprotein,

Discussion

In our study, plaques were detected in 7 of 30 patients diagnosed with nephrotic syndrome. The plaque rate was significantly higher, especially in older patients. No significant change in MPV values was observed in those with plaques. Left CIMT was found to be higher in those with plaques. When plaque analysis was performed by gender, the plaque rate was higher in women (31%). The etiology of nephrotic syndrome was known in all patients with plaques. MGN was the most common cause of nephrotic syndrome. The low prevalence of CVD, DM, and smoking in most patients probably also reduced the plaque prevalence rate. MPV was found to be inversely related to both left and right CIMT, meaning that as CIMT increased, MPV decreased. Nephrotic patients are prone to atherosclerosis as a result of frequent exposure to hyperlipidemia, hypertension, and immunosuppressive drugs. KIMK is widely used in the assessment of atherosclerosis (3). MPV is a new marker associated with atherothrombosis (6). Prolonged hyperlipidemia in nephrotic syndrome is a significant risk factor for many disease complications, including accelerated atherosclerosis, myocardial infarction, stroke, chronic kidney disease, and thrombosis. As a result of dyslipidemia, lipid-induced cellular damage to podocytes, mesangial cells, and potentially renal tubular cells appears to play an increasingly important role in the pathogenesis of nephrotic syndrome [7].

Platelets are cells whose primary function is to participate in hemostasis, which also can exhibit differences in their metabolic functions. MPV is a defining index parameter for platelet function. It has been demonstrated that MPV is elevated in diabetics with microvascular disease such as microalbuminuria and retinopathy. Many studies have been conducted on MPV recently, and attempts have been made to identify its role in the pathogenesis of many diseases [8].

In their study, Mayer et al. investigated whether MPV predicts clinical outcomes and the progression of atherosclerosis in patients with asymptomatic carotid artery disease. A total of 1006 patients with asymptomatic carotid atherosclerosis were examined. Patients were clinically followed up for the occurrence of a Major Adverse Cardiovascular Event (MACE), a composite of myocardial infarction, percutaneous coronary intervention, coronary artery bypass grafting, stroke, and death. During a median follow-up period of 3.1 years (interquartile range 2.5-3.5), a total of 316 (31.5%) MACE events were recorded. Biochemical parameters,

estimated glomerular filtration rate, proteinuria, and MPV levels were compared at baseline and 12 months post-treatment. MPV, proteinuria, total cholesterol, triglycerides, LDL cholesterol, HDL cholesterol, total protein, albumin, and hs-CRP levels decreased significantly at 12 months compared to baseline in the partial and complete remission groups. However, MPV levels increased significantly, and only LDL cholesterol decreased significantly in the resistant group. In patients with primary NS, MPV is associated with prognosis or disease. MPV has been found to be independently and significantly associated with adverse cardiovascular outcomes in patients with asymptomatic carotid atherosclerosis [8].

Conclusion

Carotid intima-media thickness is a predictor of atherosclerosis. Some studies suggest that MPV is a predictor of severe atherosclerosis and can be used to predict and identify cardiac risks in patients with CVD. In our study, no statistically significant relationship was found between carotid intima-media thickness and mean platelet volume in patients diagnosed with nephrotic syndrome. We believe that the small number of cases in our study may have contributed to this finding.

Ethics approval

This study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the Yuzuncu Yil University Ethics Committee.

References

1. Chadban SJ, Atkins RC. Glomerulonephritis. *Lancet*. 2005;365(9473):1797-1806. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(05)66583-X
2. Mayer FJ, Hoke M, Schillinger M, et al. Mean platelet volume predicts outcome in patients with asymptomatic carotid artery disease. *Eur J Clin Invest*. 2014;44(1):22-28. doi:10.1111/eci.12184
3. Nezu T, Hosomi N, Aoki S, Matsumoto M. Carotid Intima-Media Thickness for Atherosclerosis. *J Atheroscler Thromb*. 2016;23(1):18-31. doi:10.5551/jat.31989
4. Vizioli L, Muscari S, Muscari A. The relationship of mean platelet volume with the risk and prognosis of cardiovascular diseases. *Int J Clin Pract*. 2009;63(10):1509-1515. doi:10.1111/j.1742-1241.2009.02070.x
5. Slavka G, Perkmann T, Haslacher H, et al. Mean platelet volume may represent a predictive parameter for overall vascular mortality and ischemic heart disease. *Arterioscler Thromb Vasc Biol*. 2011;31(5):1215-1218. doi:10.1161/ATVBAHA.110.221788
6. Choi DH, Kang SH, Song H. Mean platelet volume: a potential biomarker of the risk and prognosis of heart disease. *Korean J Intern Med*. 2016;31(6):1009-1017. doi:10.3904/kjim.2016.078
7. Agrawal S, Zaritsky JJ, Fornoni A, Smoyer WE. Dyslipidaemia in nephrotic syndrome: mechanisms and treatment [published correction appears in *Nat Rev Nephrol*. 2017 Dec 13;14(1):70. doi: 10.1038/nrneph.2017.175.]. *Nat Rev Nephrol*. 2018;14(1):57-70. doi:10.1038/nrneph.2017.155
8. Tavil Y, Sen N, Yazici H, et al. Coronary heart disease is associated with mean platelet volume in type 2 diabetic patients. *Platelets*. 2010;21(5):368-372. doi:10.3109/09537101003628421